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Abstract Book

The Role of Ancient Iraqi People (Sumerian, Assyrian, Babylonian and Arabian) in the Development of Medicine as Viewed by Western Writers

AL MOSAWI AJ

University Hospital in Al Kadhimiyia, Baghdad, Iraq.

Background: The region of Iraq was historically known as Mesopotamia and was home to the world's first known civilizations. These civilizations produced some of the earliest writing and some of the first sciences and medicine of the world; hence its common epithet, the "Cradle of Civilization". The aim of this paper is to study the views of the distinguished western writers regarding the role of ancient people of Iraq in the development of Medicine.

Methods: the views of the distinguished western writers regarding the role of ancient people of Iraq in the development of Medicine were reviewed and studied.

Results: Samuel Noah Kramer considered the Sumerian pharmacological tablets as the first pharmacopoeia. In summarizing the effects of Arabian in the development of medicine Stubb and Bleight stated in 1931 "With Arabs began the real craft of apothecaries". Meyerhof in 1944 wrote in his book "Pharmacology during the golden age of Arabian Medicine" "The establishment of hospitals was originated by Arabians"

Conclusions: The ancient Iraqi people played an important role in the early development of medicine.